

**NEW EPOCH IN UZBEK CINEMATOGRAPHY: MANIFESTATIONS
OF NEOREALISM IN CAMERA ART**

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ABSTRACT

This scientific article is devoted to the period of poetic cinema, which appeared in the 60-70s and is recognized as a unique period of revival in Uzbek art cinema. The article scientifically researches the films "White, White Storks", "Man Goes After Birds" created on the traditions of socialist realism by the brightest representatives of this period, directors A. Khamraev, E. Eshmukhammedov, cameramen D. Fatullin, Y. Klimenko and other artists. At the same time, the poetic orientation and lyricism reflected in these films are analyzed analytically. The creative research of the cameramen on the pictorial solution of films, symbolism and metaphorical elements in films are investigated.

Keywords: cinematographer, neorealism, genre, poetic, figurative

**ЎЗБЕК ОПЕРАТОРЛИК САНЪАТИДА НЕОРЕАЛИЗМ ОҚИМИ
КЎРИНИШЛАРИ**

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АННОТАЦИЯ

Мазкур "Ўзбек операторлик санъатида неореализм оқими кўринишлари" номли илмий мақола ўзбек бадиий кино санъатида 60-70 йилларда юзага келган ва ўзига ҳос уйғониш даври сифатида эътироф этиладиган поэтик кино даври ҳақидадир. Мақолада ушбу давр намоёндаларининг, хусусан кинорежиссёрлар

А.Хамраев, Э.Эшмухаммедов, кинооператорлар Д.Фатхуллин, Ю.Клименко ва бошқалар томонидан поэтикага бой кўринишда, ижтимоий реализм оқимининг анъаналари асосида яратилган “Оқ қушлар, оппоқ қушлар”, “Инсон қушлар ортидан боради” каби фильмлар илмий тадқиқ этилган. Шу билан бирга ушбу фильмларда ўз аксини топган поэтик, назмий йўналиш ва лиризм кўринишлари таҳлилий ўрганилган, операторларнинг фильмлар тасвирий ечими устидаги ижодий изланишлари, фильмлардаги рамзийлик ва метафорик элементлар тадқиқ этилган.

Калит сўзлар: оператор, неореализм, жанр, поэтика, ифодалилиқ

**НОВАЯ ЭПОХА В УЗБЕКСКОМ КИНОИСКУССТВЕ:
ПРОЯВЛЕНИЯ ТЕЧЕНИЯ НЕОРЕАЛИЗМА В ОПЕРАТОРСКОМ
ИСКУССТВЕ**

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АННОТАЦИЯ

Данная научная статья посвящена периоду поэтического кино, появившемуся в 60-70-е годы и признаному уникальным периодом возрождения в узбекском художественном кино. В статье научно исследованы фильмы «Белые, белые аисты», «Человек ухаживает за птицами» созданные на традициях соцреализма ярчайшими представителями этого периода, режиссерами А.Хамраевым, Э.Эшмухаммедовым, кинооператорами Д.Фатуллиным, Ю.Клименко и другими художниками. В то же время аналитически исследуются поэтическая направленность и лиризм, отраженные в этих фильмах. Исследуются творческие изыскания операторов над изобразительным решением фильмов, символизм и метафорические элементы в фильмах.

Ключевые слова: оператор, неореализм, жанр, поэтика, изобразительность

Introduction

The development of society cannot be imagined without art. Especially, the art of cinema has a spiritual impact on human's heart and mind. When cinema was invented, the great French painter Cezanne recognizing and acknowledging its true nature and boundless power said, " ...From this day, our art (painting) will decline because cinema was born ..." [1, p.12], and emphasized the popularity of film.

Nowadays, the leading countries in the world possess their own national cinematography. By XXI century which is being described as the age of information today, unprecedented achievements have been achieved in the field of world cinema industry. Films that have risen from ordinary tape to 3D and 5D formats in many senses have the power to capture the human mind. Plots that amaze the human mind were created with the help of new, fast, convenient and high-quality techniques in the films. Thus, a "new era" in world cinema emerged. Film, now a product of huge industries, has evolved from art to industry. Industry, on the other hand, is an event in its own right to achieve economic and political goals.

Since the years of independence, the era of free creativity for the art of cinema has begun in our country. Convenient creative opportunities were created for our talented young people who contribute to the development of not only screen art, but all types of art as well. Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 9, 1992 "Improvement of the cinematography industry" with cinema was erected as a separate network system, March 16, 2004 Decree "On improvement of management in the field of cinematography" on March 17, 2004 to establish the National Agency "Uzbekkino" its adoption was the basis for the proliferation of private film studios in the efforts to the national cinematography. ¹

To date, the number of organizations licensed to produce film and video products in Uzbekistan has reached 700. More than 50 feature films are shot and released in

¹ [Возможности кинооператора в создании графического образа в узбекских исторических фильмах](#)

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https://scholar.google.ru/citations?view_op=view_citation&hl=ru&user=i_O1s8IAAAAJ&citation_for_view=i_O1s8IAAAAJ:W7OEmFMyl1HYC

Uzbekistan every year. The repertoire of more than 160 cinemas in Uzbekistan is based on Uzbek as well as foreign films. As a result, the creative competition that formed the basis for the development of the national cinematography began to intensify. The field of cinematography which is the basis of the art of the cinema has also changed radically under the influence of the development of the technology. Today, issues such as the visual expressiveness, the lack of meaning in the films, the monotony in the work of cinematographers, shallowness have become very relevant.

Methods

Descriptive, classification, historical-comparative, contextual and complex methods of analysis were used to cover the topic of this scientific article.

Given the complex content of the phenomenon of screen culture, in the work uses the methodological tools of the humanities - art history, psychology, sociology, communication theory, cultural studies. Modern art methods aimed at theoretical and historical-artistic understanding of the problems considered in the study, including: method of artistic-methodical analysis of specific artistic-expressive means created by means of cinematographic means, identification and analysis of basic non-traditional forms of screen image creation by technical and technological means methods such as the typological method were used.

In general, the work used an integrated approach to the problem of creating and feeling the specific means of expression of the screen, which allows the use of comparative analysis and typological generalization. The method of comparative analysis has been used to study the interaction of the visual solution in feature films at different stages of the development of screen art and the technological possibilities of its implementation.²

² [ПРОЯВЛЕНИЕ ЭЛЕМЕНТОВ НЕОРЕАЛИЗМА В ОПЕРАТОРСКОМ ИСКУССТВЕ УЗБЕКИСТАНА](#)

ИМ Меликузиев

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RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Since the 1960s, a number of talented young artists - directors, screenwriters, cameramen and artists - have entered Uzbek cinema, and since then a new era has begun, which has left a significant mark on the development of Uzbek national cinema.

In feature cinema, graduates of the All-Union State Institute of Cinematography young directors D.Salimov, A.Khamraev, E.Eshmuhamedov entered the Uzbekfilm film studio with their new theme, new worldview and, most importantly, modern creative methods.

At the same time, young and talented operators, such as H. Fayziev, D. Fatkhullin, L. Travitsky, T. Eftimovsky, A. Ismailov, A. Antipenko, Yu. Klimenko, G. Tutunov, most of whom are graduates of All-Union State Institute of Cinematography, and E. Kalantarov, N. Film artists such as Rakhimbaev, V. Dobrin, S. Ziyamuhamedov, B. Nazarov also joined the ranks of Uzbek filmmakers. From the very beginning of their creative work, they began to show themselves as very talented and innovative creators. A completely new style can be observed in the work of these young artists. They ushered in a new era that left a deep mark on Uzbek cinema.

Modern theme is "White birds, white birds" by director A.Khamraev, cameraman D.Fathullin and artist Sh.Abdusalomov, director Sh.Abbasov and cameraman M.Penson's "Clarity", director L.Fayziev's "Titmouse", R.Botirov's "Rope walkers" U.Nazarov's "Boy and girl", A.Khachaturov's "Conscience", D.Salimov's "Circle", H.Fayziev's "Koniyyut's secret", director E.Eshmuhamedov, cameramen D.Fatkhullin and G.Tutunov's "Elegance", The film "Lovers" continued.

Along with the increase in the production of films, their subject and genre circles have expanded significantly. A number of interesting and major feature films, documentaries have seen the screen. In many films, the modern theme has found its artistic expression. It was created its own new visual solution, films in the poetic direction. The films, created mainly by young filmmakers, enriched the Uzbek cinema in this period in many ways, contributing to its development and artistic perfection. They showed that Uzbek filmmakers have reached the level of professionalism, trying

to interpret modern issues in a new way. These films have caused discussions among a wide audience, film critics.

The poetic style can be defined in the most general sense as a combination of works that create the effect of "a unique world of images and heroes" [1, 24]. This effect can also be found in a single work in an artistic setting or in a collection of several works. Naturally, in order to understand the concept of style, the personality of the author of the work is extremely important, because the author is the main component of the artistic world of the work.

The film "White birds, white birds", created in 1966 in collaboration with the film director A.Khamraev, cameraman D.Fathullin, artist Sh.Abdusalomov and screenwriter O.Agishev, is devoted to moral issues. The film is distinguished by the originality and perfection of the literary basis, the direction, the cinematography and the performance of the actors.

The film "White birds, white birds" can be added to the list of films created in the poetic style of Uzbek cinema in the 60s. The film tells the story of two loving souls - Qayum and Malika - and their sufferings in the way of their love. According to the plot of the film, Qayum gives up the girl chosen by his parents according to the old traditions of the village and heads away from his village. In another village, where he temporarily settled, Qayum met Malika and fell in love with her. The princess is forced to marry a young man chosen by her relatives, not Qayum, and leads an unhappy life. The villagers unanimously accuse Qayum and Malika of disrespecting the ancient traditions ...

Our impressions of the film are enhanced by its rhythm, cinematography, perfect visual solution and music written by R. Vildanov, which not only adds to the events of the film, but also helps us to understand its essence more deeply [2, 72]. The camera's passing through a crowd living with its own problems and concerns, a unique rhythm, is a testament to the director's ability to take the viewer away from the main event of the film for a while. In short, such means of visual expression in modern cinema are necessary for authors to have a unique - a clearer and sharper look at the world around them. That is why, we look with special interest and excitement at the seemingly

familiar lives of the film's protagonists, but slightly altered by D. Fathullin's camera gaze. The visual solution of the film, the cinematographic work in it, delights and fascinates the audience. Operator D.Fathullin sought to create a poetic and at the same time contradictory, sharp atmosphere on the screen. He tried to create a unique pictorial counterpoint, comparing concepts such as beauty, freedom, love with the old ideas of the heretical villagers. What a quiet, magical and bright village ... Its muddy roofs, white smoke rising to the sky, amazingly beautiful scenery in each season, the dawn and the reddening sun, the dawn ... Life in this beautiful place imagined by the authors is also beautiful and had to be in harmonious and comfortable! But each time, as the Malika and Qayum lean towards each other, the "white-clad lowly figures" stand in their way. Even though the women had already stopped wearing the paranja, the old habits were still there. The authors of the film revolted against this superstition. "White birds, white birds" is not about love or beautiful human relationships, but primarily about the hatred of hypocrisy. This hatred is understandable to us, and therefore we are ready to believe in the power of love, because the script did not allow the actors S. Isaeva, B. Beishenaliev to tell more and more about their heroes. The film "White birds, white birds" ... Finally, a life and natural event is based on it, and this basis has acquired a unity and harmony with the pictorial solution [3, 17].

Picture1. Frame from the film "White birds, white birds"

There was a very heated creative debate around the film. While some supported the film because it focused on life issues and the work was based on a sharp conflict, others criticized the filmmakers for violating the criterion of reflecting the realities of life, artificially creating a complex problem environment around the film's protagonists, and exaggerating life's problems which accused of not being clear enough. Such objective, interesting ideas served as a basis for young Uzbek artists to further intensify their work, to touch on new, modern themes.

In the late 60's and 70's, Uzbek cinematographers reached a new stage of ideological and artistic maturity. Film directors K.Yormatov, Y.Agzamov, Z.Sobitov, L.Fayziev, H.Akhmar's skills and great experience, Sh.Abbasov, A.Khamraev, R.Botirov, U.Nazarov, E.Eshmuhamedov, A.Kobulov, A Innovative ideas and researches of young directors such as Khachaturov, K. Kamolova, D. Salimov

, “Tashkent – the land of bread”, “Abu Rayhon Bernie”, “Last days”, “Emergence commissioner”, “we are waiting you, boy!”, “Integral ”, “ Lovers ”, “ Meetings and separations”, “ Farhod’s courage ”, “ Man goes after birds ”, “ Bitter fruit ”, “ Story about two soldiers”, “ Kokand events ”, “ Silent boy” gave opportunities to create films like these.

Co-directed by Ali Khamraev and cameraman Yuri Klimenko “ Man goes after birds(drama, 1975) is arguably the best poetic film in the history of Uzbek cinema.

According to the plot of the film "Man goes after birds", the young poet Farrukh learns to sing about freedom from birds, and from the black people to look at the power of words and a strong hope and confidence in a bright future. He travels many arduous paths in search of happiness and truth. Farrukh, who has faced many injustices and atrocities in his path, realizes that there is no point in waiting for happiness. He swears to fight for the happiness and justice of his people with a sword in his hand ...

The film "Man goes after birds" is based entirely on figurative metaphors. Thanks to Klimenko's skill, the film created a kind of fairy-tale, light, and at the same time strong dramatic, tragic image. Klimenko has earned a strong place in the anthology of folk-poetic films with his creative work in this film. Because the talented cameraman

has created such a perfect cinematic solution that he can meet all the "parameters" and requirements of the school of "folklore-poetic" films, in particular, its high level of expression, irritating bright colors, symbolic visual language were received. However, the future of such a film was disappearing, and, unfortunately, such visual aesthetics was no longer used in films. Yu.Klimenko continued his creative collaboration with director A.Khamraev (Triptix), with Kira Muratova a completely new visual solution for his time. and created the film” Understanding white color” which has a style.

Picture 2 . “Man goes after birds”

Klimenko boldly "broke" the laws of composition. While working on the film's visual solution, he avoids the statics of classic films, takes each frame from sharp angles, has a dynamic, very free and metaphorical composition, and most importantly, reveals the film's psyche, the moods and experiences of the protagonists focused on giving. The film "About Construction" itself was "built" in the eyes of the audience. There seems to be a distinctive light, lightness and air in the film frames. Although the film's script was written, as usual, "without excess paint," the cameraman and director dressed the film's protagonists - the builders - in very bright clothes. The film was as lively and powerful as a romantic song glorifying the workers. It was intuitively portrayed by cameraman Yu. Klimenko in the style of postmodernism. Klimenko could easily enter the visual world of any director and create according to the laws of the visual world without any difficulty. Klimenko took a break after the film "Suram

Fortress". After this long break, he began working on a new film with film director Sergei Paradjanov. While working on a pictorial solution to the film, he sealed Paradjanov's color-collage style, which is inviolable with evolution, with high reverence. While working with Alexander Kaidanowski on *The Simple Death*, Tolstoy defined the stylistics of the film by subordinating it to the idea of black-and-white asceticism, taking into account the spiritual world of the work and the director's propensity for wet mysticism.

The creative collaboration of director E. Eshmuhamedov with cameramen G. Tutunov and D. Fatkhullin, A. Khamraev's collaboration with cameraman Yu. Klimenko is a classic confirmation that the film is the fruit of collective creativity.

A number of works by Uzbek cinematographers have repeatedly been awarded diplomas of national and international film festivals, state awards of Uzbekistan.

A number of Uzbek writers such as K. Yashin, A. Qakhhor, I. Sultan, T. Tola, R. Fayzi, I. Rahim, S. Ahmad, O. Yakubov, O. Umarbekov contributed to the development of Uzbek cinema. During this period, S.Muhamedov, M.Melkumov, O.Agishev, D.Bulgakov and other professional screenwriters also created productive works. Cinematographers from Moscow and St. Petersburg have also written scripts for the Uzbekfilm studio.

G.Uspensky, M.Ashrafiy, M.Burkhonov, A.Malakhov, R.Vildanov, M.Leviev, E.Solikhov, S.Yudakov, D.Saydaminova, F.Yanov-Yanovsky and other talented composers have been included in the films created by Uzbek filmmakers, and wrote songs.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it should be noted that the 60s and 70s were a period of renewal and revival in the development of Uzbek cinema, characterized by its significant growth. Filmmakers of this "golden age" sought to reveal the true truth and essence of life through their films. As they explored the subtleties of life's connections, they delved deeper into the intellectual worlds of their protagonists, continuing the best traditions of national cinema, further developing it.

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